

The Future of the New Generation of Manipuris of Assam: With Special Reference of Lakhipur Constituency (Cachar)

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Abstract:- In this article, four main basic processes of the New Generation of Manipuri youth of Assam are discussed and they are : Orientation towards future, future planning , career path , pattern of decision making. This study tries to focus on the relationship between future orientation towards family life, future planning, career path and pattern of decision making. The present study tries to get the answers of different queries like the youth's attitude regarding their future, youth's roll in decision making of their future aspirations, impact of globalization upon the youth, the way new generation is taught in school regarding their future, orientation of the youth towards their families etc. The method followed in this study was quantitative in nature. Different questionnaires were used for this purpose. A total of 50 respondents co-operated with the researcher in this study. Research on interventions in social work would be required to eradicate the problems faced by youths.

Keywords:- Manipuri Youth, Decision Making, Career Path, Family Life.

I. INTRUCTION

By “ generation” we know “ the people born and living at about the same time regarded collectively”. According to some analysts, generation is among some of the basic social categories of the society. On the other hand, some other analysts view that its significance is overshadowed by various factors like gender, class, race, education, etc. It is important to understand the orientation of the youth towards their future. Regarding achievement of desired goals, educators are responsible for rendering accurate and timely information to the current and prospective students , in an academic and professional setting. They are the ones who create the opportunities to learn various skills needed for the future by designing different assignments in this direction. It is worth mentioning that the students should be encouraged to make connection between the decisions made at present and the future perspectives. The present study aims to understand the extent the social-emotional school environment supports the educational and career goals of the youth.

As the young generation builds their individuality during the tender age, need was felt to conduct the study of the youths. Generally, cultural variables, especially the Western culture , do have impact on the future of youth in this age of globalization. Little is known in this regards which encourage us for an endeavor to understand the young minds of Lakhipur Constituency in this direction.

The Lakhipur Constituency is under Cachar District of Assam (India) .As per the 2011 Census, the total population of Lakhipur Sub-Division is 2,81,595 , where males are 1,42,855 and females are 1,38,740. The study was done with an attempt to examine the future generation of Manipuris in Assam state of India.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To understand the pattern of decision making of the new generation regarding their future
- To understand the orientation of the youth towards their future planning regarding achievement of desired goals
- To understand the orientation of the youth towards their career path
- To understand the future orientation of the new generation towards the family.

III. METHODOLOGY

Field survey was done as primary source for collecting information. Informal interaction with different people were done in addition to the formal methods like observation and interview . For getting secondary data, materials like books, social science journals, magazines, research articles, seminar reports, etc were used.

A total of 50 respondents were selected randomly for the primary data collection to complete the research. Students of age group from 15 to 25 (from class ten to twelve) were the sampling universe of this specific study. The two Manipuri villages of Cachar District of Assam which were selected for collecting the information for comprehensive analysis and writing of this article were –

- Sapormoina (Manipuri Muslim in majority)
- Daloooram (Manipuri Meiteis, Manipuri Christians and Manipuri Brahmins).

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW

WONG (2019) stated that inspiration is what a person wants to achieve in future. Planning is the capability to establish goals or make change in the ongoing action to meet the upcoming goals. Again, anticipation is the process of connecting the present conditions and the imminent results. It is time perception which directs to a probable behavior characterized by indicating how much an individual view the future.

SULIMANI-AIDAN (2020) performed a study on teenagers lives. Two important contextual factors and their impact was a theme of the study. And the factors were-

- The sense of belongingness of them.
- the involvement of the family in caretaking process

The relationship between adolescents and mentors helps build their self confidence, relationship assistance and connects with others in their prime living environment. It was a major finding of the study.

CABRAS AND MONDO (2018) made a study regarding future orientation of the students of two European countries namely Italy and Spain . It was found that the more the students were flexible in their career, the more was the probability of better life satisfaction. The ability to adapt professionally had an indirect impact on the satisfaction level of the students. It was found that the transition from training stage to professional life was difficult in both the countries and the results of the disaster of the labor market on future career projections were comparable .

HUEBNER, LAUGHLIN ASH & GILMAN (1998) have stated some specific domains as integral parts of life satisfaction of students. Those are factors like school, serve family and the living environment.

DI MAGGIO, GINEVRA, NOTA AND SORESI(2016) have defined future orientation as “individual subjective view of the future”. According to Ginevra, there are three important processes of future orientation and they are-

- Motivational
- Affective
- Cognitive.

V. ANALYSIS OF DATA

Table 1The pattern of decision making for the future.

	Responses			
	Low	Moderate	High	Total
Frequency of Response	15(30%)	22(44%)	13(26%)	50(100%)

The table 1 shows the pattern of decision making by the youth for the future. It can be said that a worth mentioning number of respondents have an average decision making pattern which is successful.

Table 2 Orientation of the youth towards future planning regarding achievement of their desired goals.

	Responses			
	Low	Moderate	High	Total
Frequency of Response	14(28%)	24(48%)	12(24%)	50(100%)

The table 2 is a reflection of future orientation of youths towards future planning, which is presented in percentage. It is visible that a significant number of new generation has an average orientation towards future

Table 3 Orientation of the youth towards future path,

	Responses			
	Low	Moderate	High	Total
Frequency of Response	14(28%)	25(50%)	11(22%)	50(100%)

The table 3 proves that most of the youth of the new generation have the tendency to think about the near future. It is a statistical picture of the extent the potential youths’ are oriented towards employment etc.

Table 4 Orientation of the new generation towards family,

	Responses			
	Low	Moderate	High	Total
Frequency of Response	15(30%)	25(50%)	10(20%)	50(100%)

The table 4 is a demonstration of the youths’ inclination towards their families in percentage. It can be said that a huge percentage of the youths have mildly, to a certain extent, family orientation.

VI. DISCUSSIONS

Among the new generation school going youth no specific pattern of decision making could be found out. They are neither interested properly nor given any significant orientation towards decision making patterns. The youth exercises decision making in their day to day life. They are able to see the future. However, it is only to a limited extent.

A significant percentage of the new generation youths has been able to acquire the proper orientation towards future planning regarding achievement of their desired goals. They can view the future with their level of vision. They have hopes and aspirations but they seem to be short sighted regarding their future and do not have long term plans.

It is a fact that the youths, who have orientation for family life and think of applying their acquired ideas in their life in future, are substantially in number. The children need to be helped so that the effects of their current behavior can be visualized in future. Important role, in this direction to provide provisions to the children to encourage and develop

such an atmosphere within the themselves, has to be played by the guardians and relatives.

Regarding career paths, a huge percentage of the new generation has no proper future vision for themselves at all. Even those who have a vision do not see beyond 10-15 years. For making a career path they mostly copy other's ideas and tend to be fully dependent on others in decision making. Most of them see limited career options and tend to go to a job which is familiar to him or her that someone has already opted for.

VII. CONCLUSION

The study on “the future of the new generation of Manipuris of Assam: with a special reference to Lakhipur Constituency (Cachar)”, was a humble attempt to understand the nature of future orientation of the Manipuris in Assam state of India. A bright future of a community can be foreseen by its orientation towards planning and setting of goals. Special focus on the youth, who are the backbone of a nation, in the days to come, is essential. In this era of “knowledge and technology.” the future success will depend on education. Any low orientation of the youth regarding any their future should be considered a huge concern of the society. Research work for eradicating faults of youth regarding their future orientation has to be done and necessary steps for enhancement of the youths future is utmost important.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Wong T.K. Y., Parent, A.M., & Konishi, C. (2019). Feeling connected: The roles of student-teacher relationships and sense of school belonging on future orientation. *International Journal of Educational Research*, (December 2018) p.150-157
- [2]. Sulimani-Aidan, Y., Schwartz-Tayri., & Melkman E. (2020). Future Expectations Adolescents; The Role of Mentoring, Family Engagement, and Sense of Belongings. *Youth and Society*, p. 1-20.
- [3]. Cabras, C. & Mondo, M. (2018). Future Orientation as Mediator Between Career Adaptability and Life Satisfaction in University Students. *Journal of Career Development*, p. 597-609.
- [4]. Di Maggio, I., Ginevra, M.C., Nota, L. & Soresi, S. (2016). Development and Validation of an instrument to assess future orientation and resilience in adolescence. *Journal of adolescence*, 51, p. 114-122
- [5]. Gilman, R. Huebner, E.S. Tian S. Park N. O'Byrne, J. Schiff, M, & Langknecht, H. (2008). Cross-national adolescent multidimensional life satisfaction reports: Analyses of mean scores and response style differences, *Journal Youth Adolescence*. 37, p.142-154
- [6]. Ekka. B. & Sangma M.T. (2021): Future orientation and Tea Garden youth of Assam : A Case study, *International Educational Scientific Research Journal*.